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Muthukrishnan.R¹ and M.Radha²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

²Research Scholar, Department of Statistics, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

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J.Pradeep¹, E.Srinivasan² and S.Himavathi³

^{1,2}Department of ECE, Pondicherry College Engineering, Pondicherry, India.

³Department of EEE, Pondicherry College Engineering, Pondicherry, India.

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